

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 6.2

GEO/EuroGEO advocacy progress
in Arctic issues to EO community

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1. Executive Summary

Arctic PASSION as an EU action to improve the Arctic Observing System in a holistic way, has developed this by collaborating in many connections to non-European actors. This task has been driven ahead from Work package 6 as the international collaboration arm of the Arctic Passion project. The means have been various interactions in the many different communities involved. This report describes the actions taken in relation to the Group on Earth Observation (GEO). Over the past 20 years, GEO has evolved from coordinating data sharing to championing Earth Intelligence, ensuring that Earth observations (as in all our means to observe our planets state) are not only accessible but also transformed into actionable knowledge. In Europe GEO is organized as EuroGEO, coordinated by a secretariat and lead by the European Commission. As one of the main objectives of Arctic Passion, The European Commission wanted to see the community activity ArcticGEOSS lead by SAON to develop into a GEO initiative.

Arctic PASSION pursued this objective by advocating in GEO in two directions:

i) to activate more Arctic researchers to get involved with the Group on Earth Observations' (GEO) worldwide network and ii) encourage better recognition of the challenges facing the Arctic by GEO.

Advocating GEO is happening also via two routes as the project strengthens EuroGEO, the European regional structure, and Arctic GEOSS, the dedicated GEO community activity that tried to be recognized as a GEO initiative and has been able to assume status as a new form of activity – the GEO Convener in the post-2025 GEO work program. This new form is tailor-made for networks of many institutions developing EO services for a wide range of end users. This ensures GEO recognition, but this does not entail support for communications or funding. But it does better reflect the nature of Arctic GEOSS, which is a network of many active research and service institutions working for the wellbeing of the Arctic.

The Arctic GEOSS convener can propose for some of our services to become a GEO initiative, but the GEO secretariat wants for GEO initiatives to concentrate on 2-3 services at best, but Arctic Passion was developing 8 and some more are developed by partners inside and out of Arctic Passion. Progress in Arctic PASSION has been a great jumping pad for growing more GEO activities for the Arctic.

2. GEO

One of the main goals of the Arctic PASSION project is to raise the status of Arctic GEOSS from a community activity to GEO initiative. For this purpose, the Arctic PASSION project was aligned to the GEO goals of fostering new EO-based services from research activities. These are embodied by the development of Arctic PASSION's 8 pilot services. Building on the legacy of prior EuroGEO engagement, an important factor was to include co-design and societal benefit analysis in each of the pilot services. Arctic PASSION Deliverable 5.3 describes a detailed societal benefit analysis of several of these. In respect to Indigenous Peoples' views, we adapted further to strengthen co-production aspects, to emphasize the equal role of local communities and researchers in the services. So, from the point of advocating GEO to arctic researchers, the whole project is devised according to the GEO strategy and with the aim of raising the status of Arctic GEOSS as the lasting organization for the Arctic EO services and foremost the services developed in Arctic PASSION.

2.1 GEO weeks and the GEO Global Forum

The 'GEO weeks' organized by GEO during the lifetime of our project have been taking place either online or in person in Africa. The 2021 online event came very soon after the kick-off of the Arctic PASSION project in September 2021, so we just participated as attendants to sessions on climate action or essential variables. But this interaction already sparked good participation of Arctic PASSION representatives in the GEO mainstreaming of essential variables.

At the 'GEO week' 2022 in Ghana, we organized a session for Arctic GEOSS together with the GEO Mountains initiative in a good collaboration with North American partners from the US and Canada. Attendance was lower than we had hoped for but, the interaction with

the small attendance was deeper than usual, with fresh perspectives from people unfamiliar to the Arctic.

At the 'GEO week' 2023 in South Africa, which included a GEO Ministerial meeting, we organized a booth and presented the pilot services to attendees – this garnered a high level of interest, including from individuals outside of the Arctic research body. On every coffee break during the 4 days of open exhibition we presented one of the pilots that had prepared e-posters for this event. Our monitor looped through all the posters in addition to some Finnish e-posters from the EuroGEO climate action

group. Our involvement even attracted the Finnish ambassador to South-Africa to join the event and be staged on the ministerial panel.

Finally, in May 2025 there was the GEO Global Forum in Rome. It commemorated the 20 year existence of the Group on Earth Observation and kicked off the third decade of GEO. Arctic PASSION contributed to joint sessions with GEO Mountains, to the GEO working groups planning session and to Action group sessions at the European pavilion. Attendance was strong.

2.2 Essential Variables (EV)

We contributed several chapters into a [report](#) lead by Gregory Giuliani at the University of Geneva. We provided significant input on EVs for the cryosphere and the general new concept SAON has developed for Shared Arctic Variables, which has also been supported through other Tasks in Arctic PASSION's WP6. It included with our contributions the move from Essential Arctic Variables to Shared Arctic Variables explained in [Starkweather et al 2021](#). It will be interesting to follow up in our Arctic GEOSS activities when our first SAV proposals will be published as GEO might be an important network to find implementation partners for SAVs. This is detailed more in the Arctic Passion deliverable D6.7. . There is a very wide interest for this for example in the GEO Mountains initiative or with the Life Watch, ELTER and other ecosystem networks.

2.3 Initiative status

From the start of the project GEO had three forms of GEO activities: community activities which were freely organized bottom-up actions; GEO Initiatives, who got some recognition from GEO for their actions and GEO Flagships, which GEO hoped for all activities to develop to. In the time of Arctic PASSION's activities, GEO has ceased to recognize community activities in 2022 while introducing Pilot initiatives instead and in 2025 added another form in GEO Conveners. So, our strive for recognition at Initiative status has been a challenge of moving targets.

In the GEO work program for 2022-2025 Arctic GEOSS was raised in status from a "Community Activity" to a "Pilot initiative" based on some of the Arctic PASSION pilot services being introduced as Arctic GEOSS services. This was in contrast to the expectation of being recognised at the level of "GEO Initiative" status as having continuous services to end-users was expected for Initiatives. Arctic GEOSS was accepted with a classification at only Pilot Initiative level, which is expected to develop further to achieve a full GEO initiative. Further details on this process and its outcomes are provided in Annex 2 and the D6.7 deliverable.

2.4 Advocating GEO to arctic EO actors

Within the Arctic Passion consortium very few of the partners had any GEO connection or even awareness. In each of the general assembly's GEO awareness has been raised by WP6 presentations or in special sessions in Arctic PASSION assemblies as demonstrated at the Baveno

GA in 2022. The session was targeted toward each of the pilot service leads to highlight why Arctic PASSION is digging into the value chain and end user links for each Pilot Service. The background we provided, about GEO strategies and EuroGEO process developments for co-design, has led to a much better understanding of GEO actions and increased motivation for engagement with these initiatives. This developed into a multitude of e-posters being provided by the services for the EuroGEO workshops and GEO weeks. Furthermore, GEO awareness has also been raised towards the many external guests from North America and Asia which attended our General Assemblies.

3. EuroGEO

A primary driver for developing EO services from European research activities comes based on GEO strategies from the European regional GEO (EuroGEO). Here Arctic PASSION is currently operating the climate action group – this is a natural fit, as all environmental issues in the Arctic are primarily challenged by the much faster and more extensive change in local climates. Arctic PASSION carries on this task from the E-shape project that started in 2019, which had in its climate showcase 7 pilot service developments. Since 2024, EuroGEO is building momentum because of a dedicated secretariat project that the European Commission funds to improve the impact of EuroGEO. Unfortunately, the climate action group (AG) is not partnered within the project, so there is demand on what the AG as a Arctic PASSION action should do for EuroGEO, but not enough resources to help the AG to do it. As the Arctic PASSION project is nearing its conclusion, the surge in EuroGEO requests will not be met completely unless fresh EC funding is also directed towards climate action group activities.

3.1 EuroGEO workshops

Arctic PASSION has participated to the workshops in 2022 in Athens, 2023 in Bolzano and 2023 in Krakow. In 2021 the event should have been in Paris, but the COVID situation forced it to become an online event. Arctic PASSION had just kicked off, but even then, the project was presented and links for advocacy and continuity from E-shape to Arctic PASSION was established.

In Athens 2022, the Arctic PASSION coordinator Michael Karcher attended the workshop – this was a fantastic opportunity to deepen the engagement of the Arctic PASSION leadership with the GEO network and partnerships.

For the Bolzano workshop in 2023, Arctic PASSION pilot services had developed to a point where most of them presented E-posters. Three coffee breaks were filled with poster presentations of two services in each. Also, one Finnish service not being a part of Arctic PASSION was included in these presentations. All of them however represented the EuroGEO climate action group. In addition to the poster sessions, in the energy action group session “Arctic sustainable energy solutions” was presented by Mikko Strahlendorff, which included content relating to the climate action group services related to hydropower from snow.

In Krakow 2024, the climate action group had two sessions discussing the status of its actions and how to address the new GEO strategy for the years 2026-2035. A session between the energy, climate and urban action groups was organized to pave a way for an answer to the new GEO focus area on the climate, energy and urban nexus. The resulting message was that EuroGEO will have its own agenda and following the GEO plans will happen where it naturally can.

3.2 Climate action group (AG)

The annex 1 includes the report ordered by the European Commission Joint Research Centre investigating the status and paths for development of the EuroGEO climate action group. In essence, the climate action group evolved from teams that developed Earth Observation (EO) services. Initially, these teams were part of the E-shape climate showcase, and later they transitioned to become the pilot services within Arctic PASSION. There were also attempts during E-shape to expand the action group to teams working in the Framework Programme for Copernicus User Uptake actions, but in the end the active group was the one on the lead project first E-Shape and then Arctic PASSION. So, for Arctic PASSION an actual climate action group was not needed, because the WP4 (Innovating user-driven arctic EuroGEO pilot services) teams and their interactions to WP5 (Assessing societal benefit and economic impacts) and WP6 (International cooperation and clustering) functioned as actions of the EuroGEO climate action group. One main AG meeting was organized in the 2022 Arctic PASSION General Assembly, to inform the pilot service teams of GEO/EuroGEO and their aims. Then there were two assemblies

of the Arctic GEOSS governance in 2023 and 2024, which also served as climate action group meetings. Still a few active services that were piloted in E-Shape were also part of the Arctic GEOSS assemblies.

The Krakow EuroGEO workshop was an important step to define the future of the EuroGEO climate AG and it chose to merge the climate action group with the new Copernicus Climate Change Service National Collaboration Forum. In this way the climate action group will include national activities across Europe to develop climate services. In upcoming Horizon Europe calls, there are favourable opportunities to strengthen the climate action group and expand services from local to global level.

4. Arctic GEOSS

Arctic GEOSS is now recognized as a GEO Convener in the post-2025 work program. GEO is no longer updating to the work program on an annual basis, but new elements and changes can be suggested any time. This relates to Arctic GEOSS in so much that, being recognized with our current Arctic PASSION affiliation, EuroGEO Climate Action group and Finnish national actions, we are free to continue our work in our own pace. We will not gain specific support from the GEO Secretariat, but we are recognised for our efforts. We can also pick 2-3 of our services as a proposal for a GEO initiative, which the Secretariat would support with communications and help in finding funding for the efforts.

Arctic GEOSS support from Arctic PASSION will stop at the end of 2025, with the culmination of the Arctic PASSION project. The Horizon Europe CryoSCOPE project starting in February 2025 will develop some of the Arctic GEOSS services further and expand their clientele. There is still a requirement for additional follow-up project funding to be secured to support the wider aims of Arctic GEOSS to deliver Earth Intelligence for the Arctic.

5. Conclusions

The Group on Earth Observation is looking at unsure times with changes in the US funding landscape, but in EuroGEO there is a vision with the action groups to continue development and sustain services from EO. With Horizon Europe actions looking to support both the EuroGEO action groups and European lead GEO conveners, there are promising opportunities for development. As funding applied for through Horizon Europe is a competitive process, it is unlikely that the actions will be sustained fully, but bridging a good part of the third GEO decade is likely.

Annex 1 EuroGEO climate action group assessment

The study ordered by EC/JRC is available from the [GEO Knowledge Hub study records](#). Or as a pdf file from <http://hdl.handle.net/10138/592176>

Annex 2. ArcticGEOSS application as GEO *Initiative*

GEO operates with three levels of engagement: *Flagships*, *Initiatives*, and *Pilot Initiatives* under the so-called GEO *Research to Operations (R2O) Pipeline*. At the initiation of ArcticPASSION, ArcticGEOSS was a so-called GEO *Community Activity*, and an objective for ArcticPASSION has been to establish ArcticGEOSS as an *Initiative* within GEO.

Through ArcticPASSION, ArcticGEOSS applied for status as *Initiative* in spring 2022 in the *GEO 2023-2025 Work Programme*. In the application, emphasis was on the SAON Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS) and its approach to build on a societal benefit assessment in its definition of the most impactful Arctic observations (described as shared Arctic variables (SAVs)). Three Arctic PASSION Pilot Services (Integrated Fire Risk Management Pilot Service, Pan-Arctic Requirements-driven Permafrost Service, Improving Safety for Shipping in the Polar Seas) were described as tangible outcomes for the period. The close collaboration with Indigenous representatives was highlighted through a description of the ROADS collaboration with the *Research Networking Activities in Support of Sustained Coordinated Observations of Arctic Change (RNA CoObs)* and its support for the activity *Support Indigenous food security and food sovereignty in the Pacific Arctic sector*.

GEO accepted the application for the *GEO 2023-2025 Work Programme* as a *Pilot Initiative* and a series of activities were initiated to address the points raised in the GEO review of the application.

The *Post-2025 GEO Work Programme* was the follow-up to the *GEO 2023-2025 Work Programme*, and through ArcticPASSION, ArcticGEOSS applied for status as *Initiative* in autumn 2024. The application had emphasis on seven of the ArcticPASSION Pilot Services and three national services that were contributions to EuroGEO. In the review, GEO requested that there should be a prioritization of the services so that they met requirements of only up to 3 services as part of an application. Alternatively, the advice from GEO was that ArcticGEOSS instead should seek acceptance as a *Convener*, which is a category designed to facilitate connection and collaboration. ArcticGEOSS obtained this status in May 2025.

The *Post-2025 GEO Work Programme* has an “evergreen” programme cycle, meaning that ArcticGEOSS at any point in time can submit an *Initiative* application for evaluation by the *GEO Programme Board*. The advice from GEO is that such an application should reduce the number of services to two or three. This opportunity will most likely be pursued.

